

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DEVELOPING READING MATERIALS FOR EFL CLASSROOMS: REVIEW AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19160517>

Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence is becoming an essential tool in language teaching and it has started to be used to develop materials according to students' linguistic needs. This article reviews modern research trends devoted to utilizing AI to create reading texts to teach English as a foreign language. The main focus is given to pedagogical advantages AI-assisted materials and how it promotes better understanding of the written texts, expanding vocabulary range. Review results demonstrate AI enabled to adapt texts to different levels, provide glossaries and automatically create exercises based on them. However, some challenges appear while relying on AI tools such as accuracy and reliability of the adapted texts as well as access to technology in different parts of the country.

Key words: Artificial intelligence(AI), adapting reading materials, digital education, reading skill development.

Introduction

Teaching reading comprehension is becoming challenging task not only for students but also for teachers demanding them more advanced instructions based on students' needs and background. Age of technology gave an access to an enormous data of learning materials; as a result students struggle with selecting appropriate information, filtering them and achieving deep comprehension [He,X.,2024:2]. Developing reading skill is crucial at higher education level as this demands working with research materials, international publications and professional terminology. The issue of developing foreign language teaching is gaining specific actuality and Uzbekistan started active modernization of national educational system. In addition, there is a strong emphasis on international teaching standards, trends, updated curricula and integrating technology into education. Recent studies show that educators around the world have different opinions about using AI into teaching methods. However, they are optimistic about its possibilities. Additionally, they think AI is a useful tool for activities like finding educational resources, adapting them into national context and planning classes. [Chounta, I.,2022, as cited in Shakib,S.,2023:2].

2.Pedagogical benefits of developing reading materials with the assistance of AI tools.

According to Huszti et al [2025:4] there are several educational advantages of using artificial intelligence in the creation of reading materials. AI can make differentiated learning materials that are adapted to the language needs of students. As Al-Kheresheh says: 'Personalization in language instruction is not just a modern pedagogical trend but a necessity resulting from the overwhelming diversity of learner backgrounds, abilities, and goals'[2024:1] The ability to assess in real time is another important advantage. AI-enhanced reading systems, offer instant feedback, interactive questioning, and automatic comprehension tests. Immediate feedback assists students and helps educators to monitor students' progress over time. AI-generated reading materials also substantially enhance vocabulary development. Through contextual vocabulary learning, students encounter new lexical items within authentic texts. In

addition, using artificial intelligence to adapt reading texts is time-saving for educators. Within one prompt they can modify text level according to the students proficiency level. They do not waste time on front end to simplify texts or summarize them. Moreover, AI assists collaborative learning through discussions, peer review systems, and group comprehension activities. At the instructional level, AI-driven materials can add some visualization enabling teachers to make more interactive tasks, design worksheets, and adjust instructional strategies based on concrete group of learners.

3. Challenges and limitations.

Despite many advantages that AI offer to adapt reading materials there are some drawbacks or challenges educators face while using them.

- *Neglecting culture and linguistic constraints*

While creating materials for reading comprehension, AI tools may struggle to recognize cultural norms, idiomatic expressions. As a result, it leads to misunderstanding among students when culture integrated texts implemented in a classroom[Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019:8].

- *Infrastructure Limitations*: Numerous schools, particularly in rural regions, lack the requisite technological infrastructure, including high-speed internet and contemporary equipment, to effectively use AI solutions.

- *Digital Literacy Gaps*: Teachers may need training to effectively use AI tools, as digital literacy levels vary across regions [Saminjanovna, I.G. 2025:6]. It has been concerned by many language educators that they have little experience with implementing AI tools. Teachers may reject or abuse AI tools if they don't receive enough training and continuous assistance, which would decrease their efficacy.

- *Reliability and quality of generated texts*. AI tools may fail addressing some factual examples given in the text or create questions which are not supported by the text. Educators should always check adapted texts before implementing them into the classroom.

4. Implications for EFL classrooms.

- *Text Generation and Manipulation*. One primary application of AI tools such as Chat Gpt or Gemini is their ability to produce differentiated reading passages tailored to a learner's interests and needs. This allows educators to develop contextually relevant materials that integrate new vocabulary naturally, addressing diverse student needs. [Koraishi, O. 2023:5]. If the text is given in C1 level, AI adjusts it to B2 by only one prompt. Also, it possible to give bilingual translation of the text at the same time or give translation of key words.

- *Specific vocabulary Integration*. Some texts often fail to integrate specific range of vocabulary based on the topic or difficulty level. This opportunity of AI tools is effective to integrate subject-specific vocabulary, or give them as a glossary at the end, highlight them in the text. As a result, students learn more effectively and focusing only on words that they need.

- *Specific grammar aspects integration*. It is possible to remake the texts according to the grammar topic. For instance, if the topic passive voice , AI tools can adhere more sentences by changing active sentences into passive. They are able to create new texts based on what specific grammar rules we integrate into lesson planning.

- *Tasks based on the reading passage*. AI can create diverse question sets based on pedagogical frameworks. For instance, these comprehension questions can be referenced from Bloom's taxonomy such as evaluative, recalling questions. Also, it can create multiple-choice,

fill in the gaps or true/false questions adapting them to students level of proficiency and target goals.

-*Visualization and supports.* One of the advantages of implementing AI to adapt a reading passage is that it can create a visual representation of the given text in the form of diagrams, pictures, tables, story maps. It makes reading comprehension even more effective and easy for students.

Conclusion

Integrating Artificial intelligence presents significant effectiveness while creating and adapting reading materials for EFL classrooms. This review article demonstrated that AI tools have many benefits as adapting texts to proficiency level, manipulating text vocabulary and grammar structures, generating comprehension tasks and offering feedback. These advantages reduce teacher's workload and make the instructional process more engaging and interactive. However, educators need to consider some potential challenges that AI presents. There are concerns about to what extent these adapted texts are culturally sensitive or reliable. Moreover, digital literacy of educators and infrastructure limitations must be addressed in order to fully implement them into education.

Overall, AI should not replace teacher's role in a classroom, instead they should become as "assistants" by improving classroom practice. The effectiveness of AI adapted materials depends on balanced integration, teacher training and evaluating the content before they implemented into classroom.

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